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**Long-term effects of abomasal infusion of linoleic and linolenic acids
on the enrichment of n-6 and n-3 fatty acids into plasma lipid
fractions of lactating cows**

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INTERPRETIVE SUMMARY

Long-term effects of abomasal infusion of linoleic and linolenic acids on the enrichment of n-6 and n-3 fatty acids into plasma lipid fractions of lactating cows. *By dos Santos Neto et al., page XXX.* Studying essential fatty acids transport dynamics is crucial to understanding their metabolism in lactating cows. We compared the impact of abomasal infusions of linoleic and α -linolenic on the enrichment of essential fatty acids into the plasma lipid fractions (phospholipids, cholesterol esters, triglycerides, and non-esterified fatty acids) of lactating dairy cows and evaluated their carryover effects. In conclusion, abomasally infusing either linoleic or α -linolenic increased the content of essential fatty acids in all plasma lipid fractions. These responses were more pronounced in cholesterol esters and phospholipids. We observed an increased content of essential fatty acids in all lipid fractions during the carryover period, with α -linolenic having more long-term effects than linoleic.

Supplemental Table 1. Fatty acid contents (g/100g) in plasma phospholipids of cows during treatment (from d 1 to 20) and carryover periods (from d 21 to 40)¹.

Variables	Treatments ²			P-value ³		
	N6	N3	SEM	Trt	Day	Trt×Day
Treatment Period						
16:0	12.8	12.5	0.10	0.15	0.08	0.93
18:0	25.0	25.6	0.14	0.06	<0.01	0.10
18:1 9c	4.41	4.13	0.15	0.29	<0.01	<0.01
n-3	2.25	4.87	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
18:3n-3	1.07	3.45	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
20:5n-3	0.26	0.47	0.01	<0.01	0.02	<0.01
22:5n-3	0.85	0.94	0.02	0.03	<0.01	<0.01
22:6n-3	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.71	0.55	0.63
n-6	46.6	43.3	0.33	0.01	<0.01	<0.01
18:2n-6	39.4	36.6	0.12	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
18:3n-6	0.16	0.15	0.01	0.35	<0.01	0.66
20:2n-6	0.08	0.06	0.002	0.01	<0.01	<0.01
20:3n-6	4.13	3.57	0.15	0.08	<0.01	0.04
20:4n-6	2.32	1.96	0.08	0.05	<0.01	<0.01
22:4n-6	0.72	0.53	0.03	0.02	0.14	0.09
22:5n-6	0.15	0.22	0.01	0.01	<0.01	<0.01
Carryover Period						
16:0	12.6	12.4	0.40	0.78	0.57	0.57
18:0	26.2	27.1	0.19	0.06	0.00	0.27
18:1	5.39	5.34	0.40	0.93	0.02	0.42
n-3	2.42	3.25	0.19	0.05	0.66	0.50
18:3n-3	1.18	1.47	0.04	0.02	<0.01	<0.01
20:5n-3	0.29	0.46	0.01	<0.01	0.12	0.02
22:5n-3	0.92	1.00	0.04	0.33	0.43	0.65
22:6n-3	0.04	0.03	0.002	0.49	0.02	0.42
n-6	45.1	44.1	0.31	0.11	0.38	0.01
18:2n-6	34.7	35.6	1.95	0.78	0.13	0.61
18:3n-6	0.25	0.28	0.02	0.44	0.09	0.50
20:2n-6	0.14	0.11	0.004	0.01	<0.01	<0.01
20:3n-6	4.61	3.90	0.20	0.09	0.01	<0.01
20:4n-6	2.66	1.92	0.19	0.07	0.99	0.67
22:4n-6	0.72	0.46	0.04	0.01	0.52	0.87
22:5n-6	0.15	0.18	0.02	0.31	0.04	0.69

¹ Collections occurred on d 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 16, and 20 of the treatment period, and d 22, 26, 30, 34, 38, and 40 of the carryover period.

¹ Treatments were abomasal infusions of approximately 43 g/d of 18:2n-6 (N6) or 18:3n-3 (N3).

² Trt = main effect of treatment, Day= main effect of days, Trt×Day = interaction between treatments and day.

Supplemental Table 2. Fatty acid contents (g/100g) in plasma cholesterol esters of cows during treatment (from d 1 to 20) and carryover periods (from d 21 to 40)¹.

Variables	Treatments ²			P-value ³		
	N6	N3	SEM	Trt	Day	Trt×Day
Treatment Period						
16:0	3.19	3.07	0.08	0.37	0.02	0.91
18:0	0.42	0.54	0.02	0.04	0.71	0.64
18:1 9c	1.62	1.58	0.02	0.25	<0.01	0.44
n-3	5.07	13.4	0.21	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
18:3n-3	4.70	13.1	0.32	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
20:5n-3	0.33	0.47	0.02	0.01	0.14	<0.01
n-6	83.3	75.1	0.30	<0.01	0.01	<0.01
18:2n-6	79.5	71.1	0.059	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
18:3n-6	1.57	1.39	0.040	0.04	<0.01	0.25
20:4n-6	1.22	1.07	0.04	0.08	<0.01	0.78
22:4n-6	1.01	1.02	0.091	0.94	<0.01	0.93
Carryover Period						
16:0	3.58	3.68	0.43	0.88	0.44	0.74
18:0	0.69	0.90	0.13	0.35	0.15	0.46
18:1 9c	1.82	1.87	0.35	0.93	0.04	0.84
n-3	5.57	9.38	0.18	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
18:3n-3	5.21	9.08	0.11	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
20:5n-3	0.38	0.57	0.02	0.01	<0.01	0.02
n-6	82.5	78.3	0.32	<0.01	0.15	<0.01
18:2n-6	78.6	74.9	0.41	0.01	<0.01	<0.01
18:3n-6	2.00	1.89	0.03	0.10	<0.01	<0.01
20:4n-6	1.24	0.98	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.91
22:4n-6	0.40	0.40	0.01	0.96	<0.01	0.33

¹ Collections occurred on d 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 16, and 20 of the treatment period, and d 22, 26, 30, 34, 38, and 40 of the carryover period.

² Treatments were abomasal infusions of linoleic (N6) or linolenic (N3) acids.

³ Trt = main effect of treatment, Day= main effect of days, Trt×Day = interaction between treatments and day.

Supplemental Table 3. Fatty acid contents (g/100g) in plasma triglycerides of cows during treatment (from d 1 to 20) and carryover periods (from d 21 to 40)¹.

Variables	Treatments ²			P-value ³		
	N6	N3	SEM	Trt	Day	Trt×Day
Treatment Period						
16:0	17.6	17.5	0.27	0.83	0.01	0.10
18:0	34.5	35.2	1.25	0.72	<0.01	0.42
18:1 9c	5.26	4.87	0.12	0.10	<0.01	0.92
n-3	2.39	5.17	0.14	<0.01	0.01	<0.01
18:3n-3	2.05	4.65	0.13	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
20:5n-3	0.16	0.22	0.01	0.05	0.07	0.10
22:5n-3	0.20	0.25	0.01	0.01	<0.01	0.07
n-6	16.8	14.6	1.36	0.35	<0.01	0.09
18:2n-6	15.4	13.9	1.47	0.53	<0.01	0.04
18:3n-6	0.41	0.35	0.03	0.27	<0.01	0.16
20:4n-6	0.58	0.46	0.06	0.30	0.04	0.50
22:4n-6	0.11	0.08	0.005	0.03	0.25	0.04
Carryover Period						
16:0	18.3	18.7	0.89	0.80	0.45	0.28
18:0	36.4	37.5	1.59	0.66	0.38	0.81
18:1 9c	6.24	5.31	0.71	0.42	0.26	0.63
n-3	1.83	2.38	0.11	0.04	0.03	0.02
18:3n-3	1.41	1.94	0.07	0.01	0.03	<0.01
20:5n-3	0.08	0.15	0.01	0.01	<0.01	0.16
22:5n-3	0.22	0.25	0.02	0.29	0.43	0.31
n-6	11.3	10.6	1.38	0.75	0.73	0.92
18:2n-6	10.4	8.87	1.05	0.39	0.35	0.80
18:3n-6	0.36	0.32	0.06	0.61	0.16	0.97
20:4n-6	0.47	0.35	0.06	0.28	0.17	0.88
22:4n-6	0.11	0.06	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.47

¹ Collections occurred on d 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 16, and 20 of the treatment period, and d 22, 26, 30, 34, 38, and 40 of the carryover period.

² Treatments were abomasal infusions of linoleic (N6) or linolenic (N3) acids.

³ Trt = main effect of treatment, Day= main effect of days, Trt×Day = interaction between treatments and day.

Supplemental Table 4. Fatty acid contents (g/100g) in plasma NEFA of cows during treatment (from d 1 to 20) and carryover periods (from d 21 to 40)¹.

Variables	Treatments ²		SEM	<i>P</i> -value ³		
	N6	N3		Trt	Day	Trt×Day
Treatment Period						
16:0	19.8	19.6	0.14	0.29	<0.01	0.26
18:0	32.4	34.0	0.70	0.23	<0.01	0.38
18:1 9c	12.6	10.5	1.33	0.37	0.43	0.43
n-3	1.66	3.49	0.09	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
18:3n-3	1.33	3.08	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
20:5n-3	0.09	0.16	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
22:5n-3	0.20	0.25	0.01	0.05	<0.01	0.54
n-6	12.6	11.3	0.24	0.03	<0.01	0.03
18:2n-6	11.3	9.96	0.18	0.02	<0.01	<0.01
20:3n-6	0.53	0.47	0.01	0.06	<0.01	0.02
20:4n-6	0.74	0.70	0.03	0.42	<0.01	0.23
22:4n-6	0.12	0.11	0.004	0.28	<0.01	0.04
Carryover Period						
16:0	18.2	18.5	0.89	0.82	0.02	0.46
18:0	31.8	32.8	0.59	0.33	<0.01	0.29
18:1 9c	9.64	9.79	1.13	0.93	0.14	0.73
n-3	2.16	2.82	0.06	<0.01	<0.01	0.04
18:3n-3	1.73	2.07	0.06	0.04	<0.01	0.25
20:5n-3	0.14	0.27	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
22:5n-3	0.25	0.31	0.01	0.02	<0.01	0.45
n-6	16.7	13.9	0.35	0.01	<0.01	<0.01
18:2n-6	14.4	12.9	0.97	0.36	<0.01	0.08
20:3n-6	0.90	0.63	0.05	0.03	<0.01	<0.01
20:4n-6	0.91	0.77	0.05	0.20	<0.01	0.11
20:5n-3	0.14	0.27	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
22:4n-6	0.14	0.10	0.01	0.06	0.05	0.58

¹ Collections on d 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 16, and 20 of the treatment period, and d 22, 26, 30, 34, 38, and 40 of the carryover period.

² Treatments were abomasal infusions of linoleic (N6) or linolenic (N3) acids.

³ Trt = main effect of treatment, Day= main effect of days, Trt×Day = interaction between treatments and day.